

RESULTS FROM THE GODDARD SPACE FLIGHT CENTER'S LONG DURATION EXPOSURE FACILITY SOLAR ARRAY COMPONENT TEST

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ABSTRACT

A shuttle placed the Long Duration Exposure Facility (LDEF) in space in April 1984 and another shuttle retrieved it in January 1990. The Goddard Space Flight Center supplied a test plate for the LDEF. Conductively coated covers on the test plate demonstrated that they and that several means of connecting to them withstand prolonged exposure to the Low Earth Orbit (LEO) space environment. Bare solar cells and solar cells with various thicknesses of covers provided data on cell degradation due to hard particle radiation for comparison to ground based predictions. For bare cells, the measured degradation is significantly greater than the predictions. For covered cells, the uncertainty in the measured degradation and the predictions invalidated the comparison. Solar cells covered with fused silica covers having ultraviolet filters and solar cells covered with fused silica covers without ultraviolet filters did not give useful information on the value of the filter.

INTRODUCTION

The Goddard Space Flight Center's test plate is a part of the Solar Array Materials Passive LDEF Experiment (SAMPLE). SAMPLE included experiments from the Marshall Space Flight Center, Lewis Research Center, and Jet Propulsion Laboratory. A schematic drawing of the Goddard test plate is shown in Figures 1, 2, and 3.

CONDUCTIVELY COATED COVER PERFORMANCE

The test plate contains twenty-eight two centimeter by two centimeter solar cells under conductively coated covers. These assemblies are designated as S1 through S28 in Figure 1. Electrical connection to these covers was made by various epoxies and solders listed in the "bond" column in Table I. The designation 56C stands for Eccobond 56C. The designation 56C HC means that the epoxy was heat cured. Epon 815 is a commercially available epoxy that the GSFC filled with silver. Some of the epoxies were diluted. The dilutant and concentration is shown in the Table. The terminology "solder #1" and "solder #3" are the manufacturer's designations for the solder composition. The cells under the conductively coated covers cannot be measured for electrical output. However, the covers themselves each had four electrical connections which were used both to test the covers and the connection method itself. Thirty gauge solid copper wire made connection to all the covers. As shown in Table I, some of the wire is bare copper and some is tin plated copper.

Table I provides preflight resistance measurements on the conductive covers. The preflight cover resistance values are the average of five resistances. With reference to Figure 4, these resistances are from pad 1 to pads 2, 3, and 4; and from pad 3 to pads 2 and 4. The preflight bond resistance values are the average of eight resistances. These are terminal 1 to pads 1 and 2, terminal 2 to pads 2 and 3, terminal 3 to pads 3 and 4 and terminal 4 to pads 4 and 1.

The average and standard deviation¹ of the preflight resistance measurements on the covers is respectively 5.08 k Ω and 1.75 k Ω . This provides some notion of how variable the resistance of the covers and the connection between the pads and the covers is. The average and standard deviation of the preflight bond resistances using solders was 2.42 Ω and .51k Ω . The average and standard deviation of the preflight bond resistances using 56C diluted with 10 percent toluene was 67.1k Ω and 13.1k Ω . The average and standard deviation of the preflight bond resistances using 56C diluted with 10 percent alcohol was 49.2k Ω and 12.3k Ω . The average and standard deviation of the preflight bond resistances using 56C diluted with 10 percent toluene and heat cured was 53.5k Ω and 7.4k Ω . The average and standard deviation of the preflight bond resistances using silver filled Epon 815 with no dilutant was 23.4k Ω and 9.0k Ω . From geometrical considerations, and assuming a good ohmic contact between the bond and the cover, the bond resistance values should be approximately one half the values of the resistance between the pads; this is true only for the solders. In short, the epoxies provided poor conduction to the conductive coating compared to the indium solders. The best of the epoxies, by about a factor of two, is the Epon 815. This could be because of a lack of a dilutant or because the epoxy had a different percentage fill of silver.

Table I provides postflight resistance measurements on the conductive covers. In Table I, serial S-10 lacks information because the cover was struck and broken by a meteorite. In what follows, the results from S-10 are excluded. Serial S-13, S-18 and S-22 bond resistances are based two fewer resistance readings than the other covers due to broken wires. In the case of S-22 the broken wire was due to a hit by a meteorite.

Table I shows postbond resistance measurements and corrected postbond resistance measurements. A corrected postbond resistance is obtained by multiplying the postflight bond resistance by the ratio of the preflight cover resistance to the postflight cover resistance. This compensates for any change in the resistance of the cover coating. Such a change could result from a

difference in the preflight and post flight humidity environment as the coatings are known to vary as a function of humidity or could result from a change in the coating as a result of flight, probably caused by coating erosion. As an aside, the average cover resistance increased from 5.1k Ω to 11.4k Ω and the standard deviation respectively increased from 1.8k Ω to 6.5k Ω .

Table I shows that all of the conductive epoxy bonds decreased dramatically in resistance after flight. A few of these bonds showed resistances as low as those achieved by the solders. The average and standard deviation of the postflight bond resistances using solders was 2.42 Ω and .51k Ω , exactly the same average as the preflight averages. In fact each individual reading varied no more than 2.4 percent from the preflight value. The average and standard deviation of the postflight bond resistances using 56C diluted with 10 percent toluene is 4.0k Ω and 1.27k Ω . The average and standard deviation of the postflight bond resistances using 56C diluted with 10 percent alcohol is 4.6k Ω and 1.6k Ω . The average and standard deviation of the postflight bond resistances using 56C diluted with 10 percent toluene and heat cured is 4.2k Ω and 1.1k Ω . The average and standard deviation of the postflight bond resistances using silver filled Epon 815 with no dilutant is 3.21k Ω and .63k Ω .

These results show that the indium solders provide a repeatable low resistance technique for making contact with the conductive covers. The tested epoxies presently have too much variation caused by unknown mechanisms to reliably compete with the solders. Further understanding of the mechanisms that account for this variability may render the epoxies acceptable. This undertaking did not study the mechanisms responsible for the variable resistance.

SOLAR CELL DEGRADATION

The test plate also contains fifteen two centimeter by six centimeter Spectrolab K 6.5 solar cells under fused silica covers of varying thicknesses. These cells are designated as S1 through S28 in Figure 1. Table II provides information on the measured degradation of these solar cells as well as predictions of the cell's degradation. The notations w/f and wo/f in column two of Table II note the presence or absence of an OCLI ultraviolet filter on the covers. The measured data reflects, of course, degradation due to all causes while the predicted data is for the degradation due to hard particle radiation only. The equivalent number of 1 MeV electrons due to trapped protons² and from trapped electrons³ was computed from J. Watt's data using the methods in the Solar Cell Radiation Handbook.⁴ The number of 1 MeV electrons so predicted is much less than the values obtained by using the summary tables of "Annual Equivalent 1 MeV Electron Fluence," Tables 6.6 and following, in the Solar Cell Radiation Handbook (SCRH).

A part of the reason for carrying the solar cells with varying cover thickness was to verify that the predicted degradation due to hard particle radiation was accurate. In all but the bare cell case, uncertainties in both the

measured and predicted degradations are large enough that a meaningful comparison cannot be made. With respect to the bare cells, degradation is clearly much higher than predicted degradation. This is true even if the appropriate summary tables following Table 6.6 in the SCRH are used. For instance, these tables predict a degradation of 5.1% for peak power for the bare cells. This difference between measurement and prediction suggests that some part of the method used to predict damage is not understood. Fortunately, the bare cell case is not encountered in practice.

The measured relative output of one cell to another both before and after retrieval is quite accurate. These relative outputs show increasing degradation in Isc as the glass becomes thicker. This suggests that the fused silica or its filters are darkening.

Due to the time between the retrieval of LDEF and the first measurements, many months later, ultraviolet induced damage to the DC 93-500 cover to cell adhesive may have bleached out. This means that the value of the OCLI filter cannot be well assessed. However, at the time of measurement those covers with filters showed only a slight advantage over the covers without a filter.

¹All standard deviations in this paper use the "n method" rather than the "n-1 method."

²J. W. Watts, T. W. Armstrong and B. L. Colborn, "Revised Prediction of LDEF Exposure to Trapped Protons," Proceedings from the Second Post Retrieval Symposium, NASA Conference Publication 3194, Part 1, Fig. 4, p. 144.

³J. W. Watts, T. A. Parnell, J. H. Derrickson, T. W. Armstrong, and E. V. Benton, "Prediction of LDEF Ionizing Radiation Environment," Proceedings from the First Post Retrieval Symposium, NASA Conference Publication 3134, Part 1, Fig. 5, p. 221.

⁴H. Y. Tada, J. R. Carter, B. E. Anspaugh, and R. G. Downing, *Solar Cell Radiation Handbook*, Third Edition, JPL Publication 82-69, November 1, 1982.

Table I
Summary of Conductive Cover Configuration and Results

Cover ID	Bond	Epoxy Thinner or Solder Composition	Wire	Cover Resistance (k Ω)		Bond Resistance (k Ω)			
				Preflight	Postflight	Preflight	Postflight	Corrected Postflight	Postflight/Preflight
S-1	56C	10% Toluene	Bare	7.61	6.13	47.48	4.83	6.00	.126
S-2	56C	10% Alcohol	Bare	9.59	10.87	73.57	7.26	6.40	.087
S-3	56C HC	10% Toluene	Bare	8.34	10.70	42.08	7.46	5.82	.138
S-4	EPON 815	No Thinner	Sn Plated	3.45	4.14	11.69	3.42	2.85	.244
S-5	Solder #1	50%In 50%Sn	Sn Plated	5.69	6.15	3.06	3.34	3.09	1.011
S-6	Solder #3	90%In 10%Ag	Sn Plated	4.24	4.15	2.33	2.32	2.37	1.018
S-7	56C	10% Toluene	Bare	4.03	8.53	66.72	6.24	2.95	.044
S-8	56C	10% Alcohol	Bare	4.71	15.71	45.12	11.68	3.50	.078
S-9	56C HC	10% Toluene	Bare	5.29	16.09	62.38	12.22	4.02	.064
S-10	EPON 815	No Thinner	Bare	9.42	N/A	33.92	N/A	N/A	N/A
S-11	Solder #1	50%In 50%Sn	Sn Plated	3.81	9.91	2.13	5.52	2.12	.997
S-12	56C	10% Toluene	Bare	3.42	8.72	69.13	6.43	2.52	.036
S-13	56C	10% Alcohol	Bare	3.19	7.44	43.26	5.79	2.48	.057
S-14	EPON 815	No Thinner	Sn Plated	3.84	8.57	17.99	6.01	2.69	.15
S-15	Solder #1	50%In 50%Sn	Sn Plated	4.36	11.28	2.47	6.38	2.46	.998
S-16	Solder #3	90%In 10%Ag	Sn Plated	5.55	15.08	3.02	7.99	2.94	.976
S-17	Solder #3	90%In 10%Ag	Sn Plated	3.43	5.68	1.90	3.12	1.88	.993
S-18	56C	10% Toluene	Bare	5.45	35.16	84.42	25.70	3.98	.047
S-19	56C	10% Alcohol	Bare	5.15	16.16	42.72	12.84	4.09	.096
S-20	56C HC	10% Toluene	Bare	4.23	10.00	56.05	9.26	3.91	.070
S-21	EPON 815	No Thinner	Sn Plated	5.66	16.55	30.17	11.99	4.10	.136
S-22	Solder #1	50%In 50%Sn	Sn Plated	6.14	18.67	3.39	9.62	3.16	.933
S-23	Solder #3	90%In 10%Ag	Sn Plated	3.69	6.13	1.97	3.30	1.98	1.009
S-24	56C	10% Toluene	Bare	5.23	13.34	67.21	8.98	3.52	.052
S-25	56C	10% Alcohol	Bare	5.86	20.77	41.32	23.02	6.50	.157
S-26	56C HC	10% Toluene	Bare	3.67	6.75	53.44	5.24	2.85	.053
S-27	Solder #1	50%In 50%Sn	Sn Plated	3.59	7.10	2.00	3.91	1.97	.989
S-28	Solder #3	90%In 10%Ag	Sn Plated	3.63	7.54	1.98	4.07	1.96	.988

Table II
Measured Solar Cell Degradation and Predicted Solar Cell Degradation Due to Hard Particle Radiation

Cell No.	Cover Thickness (mil)	Preflight Isc (ma)	Measured Isc Change (%)	Predicted Isc Change (%)	Preflight Voc (mv)	Measured Voc Change (%)	Predicted Voc Change (%)	Preflight Pmax (mw)	Measured Pmax Change (%)	Predicted Pmax Change (%)
LD1	bare	495	-5.25	-.6	580	-21.7	-.9	215	-47.9	-2.2
LD2	12 w/f	507	.4	-.1	595	-2.5	-.1	218	-3.2	-1.0
LD3	6 w/f	503	.6	-.2	591	-2.2	-.2	220	-2.7	-1.2
LD4	bare	497	-6.4	-.6	592	-23.7	-.9	221	-37.1	-2.2
LD5	40 w/f	511	-.8	0.0	594	-2.7	0.0	220	-4.1	-.3
LD6	6 w/f	507	0.	-.2	587	-1.5	-.2	225	-2.2	-1.2
LD7	6 w/f	508	.6	-.2	577	-1.0	-.2	189	-.5	-1.2
LD8	40 w/f	516	-1.2	0.0	586	-2.1	0.0	225	-3.1	-.3
LD9	12 w/f	508	-1.2	-.1	577	-1.4	-.1	200	-1.5	-1.0
LD10	6 w/f	505	0.	-.2	584	-1.9	-.2	223	-2.2	-1.2
LD11	40 wo/f	519	-1.0	0.0	593	-1.9	0.0	233	-2.6	-.3
LD12	40 w/f	521	-1.3	0.0	591	-2.0	0.0	231	-3.5	-.3
LD13	12 w/f	510	-1.0	-.1	585	-2.2	-.1	227	-3.5	-1.0
LD14	40 wo/f	521	-2.3	0.0	591	-2.0	0.0	231	-4.3	-.3
LD15	40 w/f	521	-1.7	0.0	584	-1.2	0.0	229	-2.6	-.3

Figure 1
Sketch of Goddard Solar Array Component Test Plate on LDEF

Figure 2
Cross Section of Conductive Cover/Solar Cell Assembly

Figure 3
Cross Section of 2 cm x 6 cm Cell Assembly

Figure 4
Configuration of a Conductive Coverglass